

BIT PRESERVING NON-WEB STANDARDIZED METADATA USING WEB ARCHIVE STANDARDS AND TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract – This paper presents the various reasons and decisions taken through the years that have resulted in the Royal Danish Library bit preserving metadata in a standardized way, and using web archive standards and technologies as part of the preservation. Furthermore, the paper will explain how this can contribute to exit plans, disaster plans as well as supporting analysis, search and reporting. The web archive standards included is the WARC package format and the Persistent Web Identifier (PWID). The web archive technologies will be the SOLR index and possibly tools like SolrWayback. Furthermore, the paper will summaries the challenges leading to the decisions, as well as explain the standards and data models used for the bit preserved metadata.

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I. INTRODUCTION

This paper presents how the Royal Danish Library bit preserves metadata in a standardized way, and use web archive standards and technologies as part of the preservation. The paper includes considerations and decisions made through time, as well as the arguments to broaden the use of standard and technologies from web archiving. The various considerations and decisions are included to

illustrate, what might be good to consider when planning preservation of data. This involves bit preservation of metadata, a data model including standardized metadata, and use of web archiving standards. Some of the arguments are to support exit/disaster plans and to make persistent referencing to different versions of digital material.

The paper will start by presenting the reasons for bit preservation of metadata as well as how bit preservation can be done. Secondly, the paper will present reasons for standardizing metadata before they are bit preserved, and how this can be done. This is followed by argumentation for use of the Web ARChive (WARC) archive format in different ways, and the benefits to use the Persistent Web Identifiers (PWID) for persistent identification of metadata parts. Lastly, the paper will describe benefits of using web archiving technologies, and how this use can support exit plans and disaster plans. Finally, the paper will discuss pros and cons of the different decisions, before conclusion.

II. BIT PRESERVATION OF METADATA

Bit preservation of metadata is needed to make files remain accessible and understandable. It is obvious that files can become useless without their metadata. Technical metadata may be essential for

future rendering of the files, the descriptive metadata may be essential for interpretation of the contents of the files and their value, provenance metadata may be essential for understanding the authenticity of the files, and structural metadata may be essential for knowing how files interrelate, etc.

An example from the Royal Danish Library is the Radio and TV collection. This collection consists of files with one-hour transmissions. In order to extract the program from these files, we need information about the start and end time of the programs. In Denmark, we use services like Ritzau to provide metadata about the programs. These metadata does of course include much more than start and end time, and this additional information may also be important for future understanding of the programs.

At the time of writing, the repository system holding the Radio and TV collection does not bit preserve these program metadata. Not preserving metadata is quite common in many other of today's metadata repositories as well. The metadata will instead live in the repository solution with normal backup solutions. This makes the metadata vulnerable to loss.

For various reasons backup is not bit preservation since the minimum ingredients for bit preservation are

- Number of copies
- Regular integrity checks
- Independence between copies

An essential characteristic of copies in bit preservation is that there is no primary copy, - all copies are equally worthy and their integrity needs to be checked locally as well as across copies to ensure that they stay the same. The independence is crucial both on the technical and organizational level in order to ensure that the same event or incident cannot harm all copies at the same time. This could be hardware failure, operating systems failure, virtual environment failure, natural disasters, human errors, war and much more. The Preservation Storage Criteria and accompanying usage guide [1,2] describe this in more detail. The logo¹ for the Preservation Storage Criteria group is the volcano in Fig. 1, which illustrates that even if you have a 100 copies of data, everything can be lost if you place them all close to an unstable volcano.

Fig. 1 Preservation Storage Criteria logo.

The Royal Danish Library uses the open source BitRepository.org software for bit preservation [3]. This is designed to be technology agnostic, and to support all sorts of organizational and technical independency between the copies. It was developed in the early 2010's, since we were not able to find a supporting bit preservation framework, which fulfills the requirements for security needed for archives and allowing offline copies. You can find more information about this in [4,5].

III. STANDARDIZED METADATA

The Royal Danish Library has realized the importance of standardizing metadata as a result of several experiences. The library is a result of a merge of two national libraries, which each had their own strategy for preservation of metadata using two different metadata repositories. Common for the libraries were that they planned to bit preserve metadata based on the format, which their respective metadata repositories used. One of them was based on the old Fedora platform that produced Foxml, which was a Fedora XML [6]. The other was Cumulus, which is based on a key/value format [7]. In the Fedora case, the strategy had to be given up, when Fedora upgraded to a new version that was not supporting the Foxml strategy. In the Cumulus example, it did not take many years to realize, that the key/value pairs quickly became unusable, as the keys and their meaning were constantly changed. In order to ensure long-term interpretation of metadata, a project was initiated to migrate all the Cumulus key/value metadata into a standardized form. In connection with this, the Royal Danish Library decided to structure metadata for bit preservation as illustrated in Fig. 2 (inspired by The National Library of Australia's description [8]).

¹ Illustration by Jørgen Stamp

Fig. 2 Royal Danish Library metadata structure.

As illustrated in Fig. 2 the metadata structure is based on standard metadata schemes like METS as container format for metadata, PREMIS for specific preservation metadata, and various XML based specialized standards like MIX for technical metadata [9]². However, we also found that we needed a data model for structuring metadata and different versions of metadata.

The data model for bit preserved materials is designed to be as simple as possible, and still cover various representations that may come over time due to changes as described in the iPRES paper “Preservation of Metadata - A case study of a strategy to ensure technology agnostic metadata preservation” [10].

The data model is meant to be a model that can be used independently from the metadata repository providing the data, as well as being useable for any front-end/access use scenarios, where technologies tend to shift very frequently. All kinds of changes to an object can be expressed as new representations. The data model is illustrated in Fig. 3.

Fig. 1 Data Model Entities and Relations.

The data model contains data in a way, where all digital objects are Digital Intellectual Entities. For example an image file can be both the image on its own (as a Digital Intellectual Entity), but it can also be the cover of a book, and thus an object which is a part of another Digital Intellectual Entity (for the book).

The entities are called Digital Intellectual Entities in order to emphasize that these are not Intellectual Entities in the FRBR sense [11], where Intellectual Entities can have very different manifestations. Digital Intellectual Entities have different Representations originally based on the same digital object(s). For example, a Word document with macros can have Representations through time, obviously, the original Word version, later a migrated pdf Representation (without macros) and also a Representation of a newer Word version, where the macros may work, but where page numbering and fonts may be different. However, in some cases definition of “same digital object” must be decided by a curator. For example, a digitization of a page of bad quality is one Representation, while a better digitization of the same page could be considered to be a Representation of the same Digital Intellectual Entity for the page.

A Digital Intellectual Entity is just an identifier, which will always be the same through time. Different “versions” of a Digital Intellectual Entity are expressed in its Representations, i.e. if there are changes to a Digital Intellectual Entity, these must be expressed in a new Representation for the Digital Intellectual Entity.

An example from the Radio and TV collection at the Royal Danish Library is the modelling of a radio

² Standards placed at loc.gov provides some of the examples of XML based metadata standards

program spanning over two hours. The data model for this case is illustrated in Fig. 4.

Representations contain metadata, which may be metadata for a specific file, as is the case for the one-hour chunks of transmissions. A Representation can also just be metadata on its own as is the case for the Ritzau metadata. Lastly, a Representation may point to other Digital Intellectual Entities, which is the case for the program Representation, which points to the Digital Intellectual Entity for the Ritzau metadata and the two Digital Intellectual Entities for the chunks of transmission which contain parts of the program.

Fig. 4 Royal Danish Library metadata structure.

IV. PACKAGING DATA/METADATA IN WARC

In 2012, the iPRES paper “Package Formats for Preserved Digital Material” [12] described how the Royal Library decided using the Web Archiving format (WARC [13]) as a package format for long-term preservation. A package format was – and is – needed, since, in practice, producing the XML files results in the creation of many small files. The conclusion was [12]:

“Compared to most other formats, the WARC format is strong as a preservation packaging format in general, especially regarding issues of: applying identifiers to bit-sequences/files, being easily understandable and being one of the few formally standardised formats ...”

At that stage, the Royal Library required files to be preserved along with their identifier. The reason was that the name of a file is related to the file

system and can therefore change when files are migrated to other platforms. As an example, Windows and Linux have differences between allowed characters in file names, delimiters for folders are different, case sensitivity is different etc. This was, however, a requirement that was made before the merge of the national libraries in Copenhagen and Aarhus. The bit preservation in Aarhus included petabytes of Radio and TV stored as files in three copies. In order to get a common way to bit preserve data, we had to reconsider this requirement, since it would be a huge task to migrate all these petabytes of files into WARC. As the paper states [12]:

“The requirement of expressing Identifiers for files is crucial for the choice of WARC in the present presentation. Therefore, there may be cases where such an analysis will not lead to the same result. This would for instance be the case where this requirement is seen as less important, due to e.g. relying on a bit repository to keep track of the identifier, having few formats where risk of losing embedded identifiers is seen as unimportant, or risk related to having identifiers as part of the file name is considered minor.”

Reconsideration did not include an option to accept the risk of losing the link between a file and its identifier. It was instead a question of analyzing how this link could be ensured in other ways. The conclusion was that as long as the metadata for files are bit preserved, it is actually possible to link the metadata, and thus the identifier, with the file by using the file-checksum information in the metadata. This would of course be a huge processing task, but it would be doable.

The next question was whether WARC would still be the best choice of package format, when we only use WARC for packaging of metadata. We concluded that this is still the right choice. Firstly, because WARC is easily understandable and one of the few formally standardised package formats. Secondly, we have discovered that we can probably use web archiving standard and technologies for the metadata.

Note that it was solely the conversion challenge which led to the change in use of WARC. There would be several benefits in continuing packing files in WARC. Firstly, it would still be a better way to ensure the link between identifiers and files. Secondly, as described later, it would extend the number of

features that can be utilized from WARC tools as access and search tools for the bit preserved files.

V. USE OF PERSISTENT WEB IDENTIFIERS (PWID)

Although we are not dealing with web data, the Persistent web IDentifier (PWID) has turned out to be quite useable for persistent referencing of Representation to Digital Intellectual Entities.

The PWID was invented as a supplement to existing web archive referencing standards, and includes areas which existing standards do not support, e.g. references to material in web archives with restricted access. Furthermore, the PWID is designed to be a persistent reference that is general, global, humanly readable and technology agnostic in order to enhance its chances of being sustainable [14,15]. PWID consists of

- **Archive** identification
- Identification of source:
 - **Archived URI** (URL or URN)
 - **Time of archiving**
- **Precision** (*page* or *part* (file))

For web archives, this means

- the **Archive** will be a web archive,
- the **Archived URI** is an archived harvest of a URL
- the **Time of archiving** is the time of the harvest and
- the **Precision** will either be *page* if the reference is for a rendered web page with all its referred elements (e.g. images) or it will be *part* if it is e.g. just the file with the code for the page (e.g. the html file), where *part* is also used if it is a file with an image.

For non-web archives, this means

- the **Archive** will be an identifier for the archive
- the **Archived URI** is the identifier of the resource expressed as an URN, e.g. a UUID using the UUID URN name space.
- the **Time of archiving** is the archival time of the resource
- the **Precision** will in this case always be *part*, since it will refer to a bit-stream with

representation metadata, without inherited images etc.

PWID has been registered at Internet Assigned Numbers Authority (IANA) as a Universal Resource Name (URN) Namespace [16]. URNs are names/identifiers used for internet resources, which can be compared to the International Standard Book Number (ISBN) for books. PWID URN is a formal version of PWID, which enables an algorithmic basis for finding the resource it references.

For a Digital Intellectual Entity, it will not make sense to use PWID. Firstly, because it is solely an identifier that must stay the same at all times, no matter which Representations it may have over time. Secondly, because a Digital Intellectual Entity identifier is usually provided by a metadata repository e.g. as a registered UUID. Thirdly, there are no separate packaging element (WARC record) for the Digital Intellectual Entity, since it is just an identifier. The Representations for the Digital Intellectual Entity have the content of the Digital Intellectual Entity identifier.

However, for Representations of a Digital Intellectual Entity, it can be valuable and logical to use PWID to combine the Digital Intellectual Entity identifier with the time of archiving its Representations. For example, if the Digital Intellectual Entity for Ritzau metadata (**Dig. IE Ritzau**) has the identifier *uuid1*, then over time, there may be two Representations as a result of correcting a spelling error in the metadata as illustrated in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5 Ritzau metadata with two representations.

The **Dig. IE Ritzau** identifier *uuid1* combined with the respective Representations' archival time will each form a unique URN PWID identifier, illustrated in Fig. 6³

³ The archival time will usually be with more granulate precision, but shortened here for the readability

urn:pwid:kb.dk:2015-05-06T13:05Z:part:urn:uuid:uuid1
 urn:pwid:kb.dk:2016-01-20T09:17Z:part:urn:uuid:uuid1

Fig. 6 A PWID URN example.

These identifiers follow the syntax of the formal URN PWID, where the **Archive** “kb.dk” is the Royal Danish Library archive, the **Time of archiving** is the archival time for the individual Representations, the **Precision** is part, and the **Archived URI** is the Digital Intellectual Entity identifier expressed as a UUID URN.

When providing identifiers for Representations this way, it also enables use of WARC-Target-URI in the WARC format, which is [13]:

“The WARC-Target-URI is the original URI whose capture gave rise to the information content in this record”

For web information, a WARC record contains a web element harvested from a URL, which means the WARC-Target-URI is the URL, while the WARC-Date specifies the time of harvesting/archiving what was harvested. For Representations, a WARC record contains a Representation for a Digital Intellectual Entity as it looked when archived, i.e. at the archival point in time, i.e. modification to Representations will result in a new Representation with a new (modification) time. An example of a WARC header for a Representation with metadata for a file is provided in Fig. 7.

```

WARC/1.1
WARC-Type: metadata
WARC-Record-ID: <urn:pwid:kb.dk:2024-12-05T13:38Z:part:urn:uuid:uuid2>
WARC-Target-URI: urn:uuid:uuid2
WARC-Date: 2024-12-05T13:38Z
Content-Length: 8456
Content-Type: text/xml
WARC-Block-Digest: sha-1:c925bd726bf1d575f75e1516be0ee8a4adba3762
WARC-Refers-To: file://bitrepfile/range_202412040809.mp4
Xml for Representation
  
```

Fig. 7 A WARC record header example.

Since the *WARC-Target-URI* is the identifier for the Digital Intellectual Entity *uuid2*, a search for this identifier will result in all WARC records with the *WARC-Target-URI uuid2*, in other words all WARC records with Representations for this Digital Intellectual Entity *uuid2*.

Another advantage of using PWID this way, is that the WARC record header for a Representation contains the Digital Intellectual Entity identifier it

represents. Otherwise, this information would have to be found in the PREMIS relation metadata inherited deep down in the METS metadata of the Representation. The 2019 iPRES paper on “Preservation of Metadata” [10] stated that:

“For optimization purposes, an extra WARC record is produced containing information about the relationship between Digital Intellectual Entities, each of their Representations and files (if a file exists for the Representation).”

This extra WARC record is no longer needed, since we can easily get the identifier for the Digital Intellectual Entities, and if it is a Representation of a file, the WARC record header will include a *WARC-Refers-To* with the identifier of the file.

VI. EXIT/DISASTER PLANS USING WEB ARCHIVING TECHNOLOGIES

In the Danish web archive Netarkivet, we can make a SOLR index of content from WARC files using the Warc-Indexer tools. This means we can make a SOLR index by using this tool on the preserved metadata (packed in WARC) and thus get an index of all preserved data.

The structure of all metadata is the same, since metadata across metadata repositories are already harmonised via the data model and metadata model (described above). This means that using the index and understanding the content will be the same for all the metadata.

The SOLR index also provides a way to get an overview of all the bit preserved material, independent of whether it originates from several different metadata repositories. Furthermore, it enables possibilities to make statistics and reports also independent of metadata repositories. Therefore, such a SOLR index will be an important part of exit plans from commercial metadata repositories.

In addition, it will be relatively easy to make support the full OAI protocol, which the SOLR index can support. It would also be possible to implement get Records for OAI directly on the WARC files, as the preserved metadata is written with ascending modification time (expressed in WARC-Date). Along with a naming standard for WARC-files mentioning first and last WARC-Date time, it will be relatively easy to implement for get Records (from/until) for OAI.

It will also be possible to use the web archiving tools for search and access to the bit preserved metadata by using e.g. the SolrWayback tool. However, the decision of having files outside WARC may mean that workarounds or tweaks in the tool may be needed to enable access the actual files.

The SolrWayback is based on a SOLR index generated by the former mentioned SOLR indexer tool. The SolrWayback comes with multiple features, of which the following can be useful for bit preserved metadata [17]:

- Free text search in all resources
- Export of search results to a WARC file through streaming download, which means that there is no limit to the size of the result set.
- CSV text export of search results with custom field selection.
- Visualization of various Digital Intellectual Entity statistics over time
- View all fields indexed for a metadata resource and show WARC-header for records.

If the files had been included in the WARC files, it would also have been possible to utilize features like image search, which SolrWayback offers.

In case of a disaster causing major breakdowns of a metadata repository, the SolrWayback tool can support an alternative way to find and access the bit preserved data anyway, i.e. these features can be a benefit for disaster plans.

Another advantage of using SolrWayback is that Royal Danish Library is already using this tool for web archive material, which means that there will be fewer applications in the portfolio in order to support exit and disaster plans.

VII. DISCUSSION

This paper describes a way of preserving metadata, but it is by no means the only way. It will always be a matter of risk acceptance, whether an organization decides to preserve metadata, and how to preserve them. This paper presents a case where the importance of metadata is seen as crucial, where standardization is needed for insurance of future understanding and where bit preservation must be as resilient to loss in one incident as possible.

To use a standardized metadata format for bit preserved metadata implies a decision of transforming the metadata. Transformation will always imply a risk of losing information during this execution. To the Royal Danish Library this risk is acceptable compared to the risk of getting metadata that will become incomprehensible later.

The decision making about packing data and metadata in WARC is an example where reality may cause decisions to be reevaluated. The best theoretical solution would probably be to pack files in WARC as well, but because of a cost-benefit analysis, the less beneficial – but doable – solution is preferred.

The use of PWIDs for identifiers may seem like a big step. However, PWIDs are only used as internal identifiers, which follows the way “versions” of web archive material are, and there are many benefits of using it.

The SolrWayback tool is of course made for web material, and therefore includes features that do not make sense for non-web metadata. It also uses web archive terms like “domains”, that are specific for web material. However, since SolrWayback would not be meant as a curator platform, the benefits of having a window into the bit preserved metadata will be important as part of exit plans, disaster plans and maybe even daily operations on the long term.

It is important to note that the described possible contributions to exit and disaster plans are indeed only contributions. In order to have an exit plans, plans for how to ingest and curate information for preservation are also needed. In order to have disaster plans, much more is needed, as for exit plans, other functionalities must be covered, and there will need to be plans for reestablishment of the original systems.

VIII. CONCLUSION

This paper presents decisions and considerations needed to achieve long time preservation of data along with its metadata. It describes how the implementation of these decisions can assure that metadata exists and are readable and usable for the generations to come. This involves decisions on bit preservation of metadata and standard ways to structure the metadata before the bit preservation.

In addition, the paper provides the reasons for using standards and technologies from web archiving, such as the WARC package format and the PWID identifier. It also describes how this enables utilization of web archiving tools, which can support exit plans and disaster plans.

We hope that this paper can form a basis for feedback and further discussion of securing metadata and potential use of standards and technologies from the web archiving community.

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